

Amperometric Determination of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) with Thiosalicylamide

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A rapid method for the amperometric determination of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) with thiosalicylamide at the rotating platinum electrode has been developed. Thus, 0.409 to 3.191 mg Ag(0.252-1.960 mM), 0.085 to 4.275 mg Au(0.0216-1.080 mM), 0.420 to 6.970 mg Hg(0.131-2.170 mM) and 0.071 to 1.860 mg Pd(0.0475-1.240 mM) are amperometrically determined in acid medium using thiosalicylamide as a complexing agent. All the four metals are determined in presence of large number of diverse ions, e.g., Cd(II), Zn(II), Pb(II), Mn(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Cr(III), Fe(III), Al(III), As(III), Sb(III), Bi(III), V(V), Zr(IV), etc. The relative mean errors in the determination of Ag, Au, Hg and Pd are found to be 0.078%, 0.935%, 1.362% and 0.434% respectively. The voltammetry of thiosalicylamide at a rotating platinum electrode is also investigated.

A survey of the existing literature reveals the applications of thiosalicylamide¹ (*o*-hydroxy thiobenzamide) as a successful gravimetric and spectrophotometric reagent. Recently, thiosalicylamide has been found to be suitable as a sulphide precipitating amperometric reagent² in this laboratory. Unlike thioacetamide³, which is susceptible to easy oxidation to its disulphide, thiosalicylamide solution is quite stable both in aqueous and alcoholic medium. Probably, the intramolecular H-bond from the ortho OH inhibits the process of easy oxidation of thiosalicylamide.

In the present investigation, thiosalicylamide has been used in the amperometric determination of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) at the rotating platinum electrode. In acid medium, the metals form water insoluble complexes with thiosalicylamide. From the titration results, the mole ratio of metal-ligand in the complexes of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) were determined and found to be 1 : 1, 1 : 3, 1 : 2, and 1 : 4 respectively, which corroborated the earlier results observed in this laboratory¹. Silver and mercury complexes of thiosalicylamide are white in colour, while those of gold and palladium are orange yellow and yellow respectively. Compared to earlier investigations⁴⁻⁷ for the amperometric determinations of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II), the present method is sufficiently sensitive and effective, particularly in presence of large number of diverse ions.

In the voltammetry of thiosalicylamide, the variation of the anodic current with respect to the potential applied on the rotating platinum electrode at different acidities has been investigated.

Experimental

Reagent and Chemicals :

Thiosalicylamide was prepared and purified⁸. One hundred millilitre standard thiosalicylamide solution (0.05M) was prepared in 20% ethanol and the weaker solutions were made with proper dilution. The strength of thiosalicylamide solution was checked by iodimetry¹. The stock solutions of AgNO₃, AuCl₃, HgSO₄, and PdCl₂ were prepared in double distilled water and the metals were estimated by the usual gravimetric methods.

Apparatus :

The voltammetry studies were carried out in Radelkis pen recording polarograph (Type OH 101/1). Amperometric titrations were performed with Toshniwal manual polarograph. Cambridge pH meter (Bench Model) was used for measuring pH.

Voltammograms of thiosalicylamide :

The voltammograms of thiosalicylamide were recorded at rotating platinum electrode in KCl (0.50 M) supporting electrolyte at 25°, while the pH were maintained by HCl and citric acid-Na₂HPO₄ buffer (Fig. 1). On applying an external potential of magnitude zero(0) to 1.10 volt (vs. S.C.E), the *i-v* curves of thiosalicylamide shows two waves. On increasing pH, both the waves were shifted towards more negative potential. The voltammograms of thiosalicylamide at different concentrations were recorded at 25° and it was found that the limiting currents were proportional to the concentrations of thiosalicylamide (1.00 mM-0.05 mM).

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Fig. 1. Voltammogram of thiosalicylamide at R. P. E

Procedures of amperometric titrations :

An aliquot of the metal solution was taken into a three necked titration cell in which successively requisite amount of acid and supporting electrolyte were added followed by dilution to a definite volume (about 14-20 ml). The acidities of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) solutions were 4N H₂SO₄, 3N HCl, 0.126 N HCl and 4N HCl respectively. The cell was then placed in a thermostat, at 30°. The silver solution was deaerated by passing pure nitrogen, while no such deaeration was required in the cases of Au, Hg and Pd. Meanwhile, the rotating platinum electrode and the saturated calomel electrode were introduced inside the solution through the necks of the cell. The platinum electrode was rotated at a constant speed of 810 r.p.m. and the titration potential (+0.20 volt, +0.60 volt, +0.60 volt and +0.70 volt for Ag, Au, Hg and Pd respectively) was applied to the indicator electrode. The metal was then titrated with a standard solution of thiosalicylamide (0.001M-0.05M), added through the third neck of the cell and the insoluble metal complex was precipitated. The titration was carried out until either the residual current

(in case of Ag) or appreciable high current (in cases of Au, Hg and Pd) were recorded. The end points were obtained from the L-shaped (for Ag) or inversely L-shaped (for Au, Hg and Pd) titration curves (Fig. 2) after due correction due to volume changes. At +0.20 volt (vs. S.C.E), silver exhibits diffusion current on a platinum anode but the ligand is not oxidised. On the other hand, at about +0.60 volt (vs. S.C.E), gold, mercury and palladium are not electroactive but the ligand exhibits limiting current.

Fig. 2. Amperometric titration curves

For interference studies, known amounts of the foreign ions were added to a given amount of metal ion and the metal was titrated following the procedure as described above.

TABLE I—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) AND Pd(II) WITH THIOSALICYLAMIDE

Ag taken (mg)	0.409	0.640	0.896	1.021	1.280	2.560	3.191
Ag found (mg)	0.400	0.630	0.890	1.030	1.280	2.560	3.250
Error (mg)	-0.009	-0.010	-0.006	+0.009	0.000	0.000	+0.059
Au taken (mg)	0.085	0.214	0.427	0.855	1.282	3.420	4.275
Au found (mg)	0.086	0.210	0.433	0.874	1.300	3.425	4.272
Error (mg)	+0.001	-0.004	+0.006	+0.019	+0.018	+0.005	-0.003
Hg taken (mg)	0.420	0.560	0.840	1.390	2.790	5.580	6.970
Hg found (mg)	0.370	0.520	0.850	1.360	2.780	5.600	7.200
Error (mg)	-0.050	-0.040	+0.010	-0.030	-0.010	+0.020	+0.230
Pd taken (mg)	0.071	0.115	0.230	0.460	0.920	1.170	1.860
Pd found (mg)	0.085	0.122	0.229	0.464	0.912	1.130	1.800
Error (mg)	+0.014	+0.007	-0.001	+0.004	-0.008	-0.040	-0.060

TABLE 2—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) AND Pd(II) WITH THIOSALICYLAMIDE IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS

Metals taken : 1.280 mg Ag, 0.855 mg Au, 2.790 mg Hg, 0.460 mg Pd

Diverse ion added	Ag found (mg)	Error (mg)	Au found (mg)	Error (mg)	Hg found (mg)	Error (mg)	Pd found (mg)	Error (mg)
Fe ³⁺	1.296 (3.00)	+0.016	0.861 (27.50)	+0.006	2.84 (34.46)	+0.05	0.461 (34.46)	+0.001
Co ²⁺	1.274 (6.40)	-0.006	0.867 (25.70)	+0.012	2.86 (20.99)	+0.07	0.460 (32.24)	0.000
Ni ²⁺	1.290 (6.20)	+0.010	0.857 (30.30)	+0.002	2.80 (38.06)	+0.01	0.458 (38.06)	-0.002
Cd ²⁺	1.274 (7.50)	-0.006	0.864 (15.00)	+0.009	2.82 (61.20)	+0.03	0.466 (45.00)	+0.006
Zn ²⁺	1.290 (9.00)	+0.010	0.864 (32.20)	+0.009	2.80 (22.64)	+0.01	0.461 (22.64)	+0.001
Pb ²⁺	1.285 (5.00)	+0.005	—	—	—	—	—	—
Al ³⁺	—	—	0.854 (16.10)	-0.001	2.84 (20.22)	+0.05	0.466 (20.22)	+0.006
Bi ³⁺	1.274 (17.00)	-0.006	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sb ³⁺	1.285 (12.50)	+0.005	—	—	2.82 (53.39)	+0.03	—	—
As ³⁺	1.30 (9.00)	+0.02	—	—	2.78 (41.92)	-0.01	—	—
Cr ³⁺	1.274 (5.20)	-0.006	0.861 (26.20)	+0.006	2.78 (32.80)	-0.01	0.466 (32.80)	+0.006
Mn ²⁺	1.285 (14.56)	+0.005	0.867 (35.00)	+0.012	2.85 (43.65)	+0.06	0.461 (43.65)	+0.001
V ⁵⁺	1.301 (10.00)	+0.021	0.854 (8.40)	-0.001	—	—	—	—
Zr ⁴⁺	—	—	0.861 (18.70)	+0.006	—	—	—	—
PO ₄ ³⁻	1.279 (26.53)	-0.001	—	—	2.86 (35.20)	+0.07	0.464 (35.20)	+0.004

N.B. The figure within parenthesis show the amount of foreign ion added, in mg.

Results and Discussion

The results of the amperometric determination of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) are shown in (Table 1). The metals can be estimated in presence of large amounts of different foreign ions as shown in Table 2. However, Cu(II), Tl(III), Se(IV), Te(IV) etc. interfere in the determination of the above four metals.

Accuracy and Precision :

The relative mean error and the coefficient of variation of Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) estimations are calculated from ten experiments under identical conditions, using 1.280 mg Ag in 15 ml, 0.855 mg Au in 20 ml, 2.790 mg Hg in 16 ml and 0.460 mg Pd in 14 ml. The relative mean errors for Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) are 0.078%, 0.935%, 1.362% and 0.434% respectively. The coefficient of variations for Ag(I), Au(III), Hg(II) and Pd(II) are 0.629%, 0.444%, 0.905% and 0.709% respectively.

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